

THE IMPACT OF SOCIAL INTERACTION ON LANGUAGE LEARNING.

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Abstract:

This article highlights the important role of relationships in language learning. Through a comprehensive review of existing literature and case studies, this article examines how human interaction facilitates language learning, cultural interaction, feedback and correction, increases motivation and confidence, and provides cognitive benefits. Discussing the transformative effects of human interaction on language learners, emphasizing its importance for language development, cultural understanding and intellectual development.

Keywords: language learning, interpersonal, communication, cultural interaction, thinking, motivation, intellectual interest

Introduction:

Language acquisition is a multifaceted process that involves several dimensions, including language proficiency, cultural understanding, and cognitive development. Central to this approach is social interaction, which serves as a catalyst for language learning and a conduit for cultural interaction. This article examines the dynamics of human interaction in language learning and analyzes how this affects students' language skills, cultural competence, motivation, and cognitive skills. This article attempts to highlight the importance of interpersonal communication in developing language proficiency and fluency by examining the interaction between interpersonal communication and language acquisition.

Literature Review:

Many studies have demonstrated the important role of positive relationships in language learning. Vygotsky's social theory emphasizes the role of human interaction in cognitive development and suggests that language learning, among other things, occurs within a culture. Long's Interaction Hypothesis further supports this idea by showing that strong communication in the target language enhances the language's ability to express discursive possibilities that can be understood through interlocutors' ideas.

See also Corrective Thoughts on Language Processing, which emphasizes the importance of social interaction in the fluency and disfluency process. Research by Lyster, Ranta and Ellis highlights the role of feedback from peers, teachers and the native language system in supporting inexperienced people to discover and make errors in language production. Additionally, interpersonal interaction serves as a source of motivation and self-confidence for language learners, as demonstrated by Deci's and Ryan's Self-Determination Theory, which emphasize the importance of self-motivation in language learning.

Additionally, positive interactions provide cultural immersion and understanding of the target language. Students learn about culture and language traditions by conversing with native speakers and participating in cultural events. This cultural interaction not only increases understanding but also fosters understanding and appreciation of different linguistic and cultural practices.

Methods:

The methodology used in this article includes a comprehensive review of existing literature and research on the effects of social interaction on language learning. A systematic search of academic databases, including Google Scholar, JSTOR, and PubMed, was conducted using keywords such as “language learning,” “social interaction,” “communication,” “cultural interaction,” “ideas,” “motivation.” benefits of knowing Relevant articles, research pages, and book chapters have been selected based on the relevance of the topics and their contribution to understanding the role of social interaction in language acquisition.

Results and Discussion:

The results of the literature review show that human interaction plays an important role in language acquisition in many areas. First, oral exchange improves fluency and fluency by providing opportunities to practice listening, speaking, reading, and writing in real life. Additionally, human interaction allows for immersion in culture, exposing the novice to a unique language, dialect, and culture. Additionally, the feedback and correction received at social events allows the novice to recognize and correct mistakes, leading to continuous improvement from language skills.

Moreover, human interaction provides a source of motivation and confidence for language learners, encouraging them to take risks, explore the language, and overcome the fear of making mistakes. A positive social environment creates useful knowledge about the environment and encourages enthusiasm and commitment to language learning. Ultimately, human interaction

provides intellectual benefits, including enhanced critical thinking, problem-solving, and multitasking ability through the realization of intelligence achieved through participating in conversations, discussions, and debates.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, human interaction is important in language learning because it shapes language learners' knowledge, cultural competence, motivation, and cognitive skills. By engaging in meaningful dialogue and interaction, new children embark on a transformative journey of discovery and discovery, enriched by the diverse perspectives and experiences of their peers. As teachers and language practitioners, it is important to recognize and use the power of human interaction in language integration and intercultural communication. By embracing the interplay between language and social interaction, we create a unique, comprehensive and rewarding approach to language learning.

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